

SUSTAINABILITY AND COMMONFARE REPORT

D5.4

Fig.01

Project:	PIE News – Poverty, Income, and Employment News (H2020-ICT-2015)
Duration:	1st July 2016 – 30th June 2019 (36 months)
Contract Number:	Grant Agreement Number 687922
Partners:	University of Trento, Basic Income Network Italy, Centre for Peace Studies, Fondazione Bruno Kessler, Stichting Dyne.org, Abertay University, Madeira Interactive Technologies Institute
Document Number:	D5.4
Contractual Date:	30/6/2019
Work Package:	WP5
Distribution/Type	Public/Report
Version:	Final
Total Number of Pages:	37
File:	PIE_D5.4_FIN
Author:	BIN Italia, Andrea Fumagalli, Sandro Gobetti, Cristina Morini, Rachele Serino

Abstract Deliverable 5.4 collects reflections on the promotion and sustainability of Commonfare proposal as a whole and the commonfare.net platform even after the end of the project. D5.4 includes also proposals and goals all partners have suggested in the mid-term internal report. The information and insights shared within the Consortium as well as exchanges of views with different stakeholders have led to identify different scenarios whose synthesis is the establishment of the Commonfare Legal entity Association.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Fig.02

The purpose of the D5.4 is to report the consortium reflections on sustainability of the PIE News-Commonfare project. This Deliverable, divided in three sections, refers to the Mid Term Internal Report (produced in M24) 'Promoting Commonfare', which collected experiences and suggestions from each partner on main dimensions of sustainability, so as to highlight how the Consortium has always tried to plan operational solutions in continuity with the information that came from the fieldwork carried out in the three pilot countries.

Talking about sustainability in the Commonfare project requires considering several issues. The first one is political and addresses the development and consolidation of the emerging concept of Commonfare as an alternative welfare system.

This perspective is addressed in section 1 which elaborates on Commonfare showing the influential role of the research intervention, the dissemination activities and particularly the use of commonfare.net in shaping it. The second issue is practical and addresses the interrelationship between Commonfare and social innovation. The aim of this section is to highlight how the experiences gathered during the research phase (D2.1) as well as those that have gradually joined the community of commoners can represent a feasible way to develop the welfare of the common, which can also help policy makers to achieve greater social cohesion.

Section 2 analyses this aspect by considering the general concept of Commonfare and the specific practices witnessed during the project within the context of social innovation and summarises the main themes that the Consortium highlighted when analysing the concept of sustainability. It also reports on the process involved in turning criticalities into starting points for sustainability whose core is ownership and financial independence of the commonfare.net platform.

Finally, the third section reports on the planned financial and operational sustainability model. It also describes the new legal entity established, the values underlying it, and the commitments undertaken, in economic terms, to ensure the functioning of the commonfare.net platform in the near future.

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

DATE	VERSION	AUTHOR	SUMMARY OF CHANGES
30/04/2019	V1.0A	Andrea Fumagalli, Cristina Morini	First version of the Chapter 1 and following paragraphs
15/05/2019	V1.0B	Sandro Gobetti, Rachele Serino	First version of the Chapter 2 and following paragraphs
27/05/2019	V1.1A	Maurizio Teli	Internal review
10/06/2019	V1.1	Sabrina Del Pico	Internal review
21/06/2019	V1.2	Andrea Fumagalli, Sandro Gobetti, Cristina Morini, Rachele Serino	Completed internal revision
30/06/2019	FIN	Antonella De Angeli, Stefano De Paoli	Final version with full VIGs adoption

CONTRIBUTORS

FIRST NAME	LAST NAME	ORGANIZATION	CONTRIBUTION
Andrea	Fumagalli	BIN Italia	Author
Sandro	Gobetti	BIN Italia	Author
Cristina	Morini	BIN Italia	Author
Rachele	Serino	BIN Italia	Author
Sabrina	Del Pico	BIN Italia	Internal Reviewer
Maurizio	Teli	M-ITI	Internal Reviewer
Antonella	De Angeli	University of Trento	Internal Reviewer
Stefano	De Paoli	Abertay University	Internal Reviewer

ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	MEANING
AU	Abertay University (Scotland, UK)
BIN ITALIA	Basic Income Network (Italy)
CMS	Centre for Peace Studies (Croatia)
FBK	Fondazione Bruno Kessler (Italy)
DYNE	Stitching Dyne.org (the Netherlands)
UNITN	University of Trento (Italy)
M-ITI	Madeira Interactive Technologies Institute (Portugal)

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE	TITLE	PAGE
01	Workshop at Final Conference in Trento, 29 May/2 nd July 2019	1
02	General Assembly in Amsterdam, June 2017	2
03	Oltrino's stand at Final Conference in Trento, 29 May/2 nd July 2019	8
04	Oltrino's stand at Final Conference in Trento, 29 May/2 nd July 2019	11
05	Final Conference in Trento	13
06	Train the trainers workshop, Italy	17
07	Pie News timeline, Zagreb Croatia, workshop, September 2016	18
08	Network Event at Acquario Civico, Milan, Italy, October 2017	22
09	Dynamics of commonfare.net registered users	25
10	Commoners social value participation	26
11	Overview of the commonfare platform	27
12	Network Event at Millepiani coworking, Rome, Italy, November 2017	28
13	Sustainability scenario n. 1	29
14	Sustainability scenario n. 2	29
15	Sustainability scenario n. 3	30
16	Commonfare at Connect Athens, Greece, September 2018	31
17	New legal entity resources and output	35

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	2
DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY	3
CONTRIBUTORS	4
ACRONYMS	5
LIST OF FIGURES	6
COMMONFARE AND COOPERATIVE PLATFORM	8
1.1 GOOD PRACTICES AND COMMON GOODS: AN ECOSYSTEM PROVIDING SERVICES THAT CAN INSPIRE SOCIAL POLICIES	8
1.2. COMMONFARE AND SOCIAL INNOVATION.....	12
1.3 PLATFORMS, COMMUNICATION, PARTICIPATION: CREATING LINKING	14
THE MEANING OF SUSTAINABILITY FOR THE COMMONFARE CONSORTIUM	17
2.1. ATTRACTIVENESS, CRITICALITIES AND IMPLEMENTATION OF COMMONFARE SUSTAINABILITY	19
2.2.1 Attractiveness: A concept, a space, a possibility	19
2.2.2 Criticalities: Involvement, resources, distrust	20
2.2.3 Implementation: Implementation: recognising interdependence	21
2.2.4. Implementation: turning criticalities into resources	22
SUSTAINABILITY AS A WAY	28
3.1 NEW LEGAL ENTITY, PARTICIPATORY GOVERNANCE. THE SETTING UP OF COMMONFARE ASSOCIATION	32
3.2 COMMONFARE SUSTAINABILITY MODEL	33
3.3 RESPONSABILITY AND ACTION TAKEN	37

1. COMMONFARE AND COOPERATIVE PLATFORM

Fig.03

1.1. GOOD PRACTICES AND COMMON GOODS: AN ECOSYSTEM PROVIDING SERVICES THAT CAN INSPIRE SOCIAL POLICIES

Throughout the three years of research conducted during the Commonfare-Pie News project and thanks to the field research and the activations that the *commonfare.net* platform made possible, we were able to observe the width of the fabric where *commoning practices*¹ generate, grow and interact. The term *commoning practices* refers to processes of co-production, self-government and co-management of *the commons* developed by a community or a citizens' network. The good commoning practices we encountered in our investigation or through meetings and dissemination activities made us realise that *the commons* can be a variety of resources, including natural resources, urban grass-roots organisations or intangible goods (knowledge, the internet, relations). What is relevant however is that these resources meet sustainability and equity principles in relation to the mechanisms of direct participation and management. The mapping activity carried out in Italy, the Netherlands, and Croatia (as reported in D2.1² and in the first Commonfare Book Series³), as well as the collective experiences that have been progressively narrated on the *commonfare.net* platform,

1 Peter Linebaugh, *Magna Charta Manifesto. Liberties and Commons for All*, University of California, Abridged ed., 2009

2 <http://pieproject.eu/2017/03/29/d2-1-research-report/>

3 <http://pieproject.eu/2018/02/09/commonfare-book-series-1-generazioni-precarie-una-conricerca-tra-percezione-del-rischio-bisogni-emergenti-welfare-dal-basso/>

provide an important data-base of communing practices. A growing number of social, ecological and networking experiences have met on commonfare.net.

These stories include a variety of examples of communing practices. For example, there are several organisations that are strongly committed to *agro-ecological issues*, as the Mondeggi farm⁴, or Isola Pepe Verde⁵ that registered on the commonfare.net platform. These organisations are involved in recovering a nature-based culture and generating a system able to bind together different aspects: territories, communities, the environment, common access to resources, a different relationship between consumer and market. Another example is the, *social common goods* that are imagined and produced on the basis of the needs identified in various areas (education; socialising; culture; healthcare; housing; employment)⁶. This process of imagination encourage the growth of a community that, within various forms of self-regulated mutual coalition, *conceives, gives life to and takes care of* what is underused⁷. This is achieved by *regenerating* spaces and buildings as well as by *activating* people. In the regeneration process, people can use their skills and knowledge, thus enhancing and giving meaning to them - unlike what happens within institutional and traditional environments. In addition, *commons-based networks* are associated with information technologies related to the progressive development of fields associated with knowledge creation and *open-source*. In all these cases, cooperation and participation are fundamental aspects for sustaining the common and are based on voluntary contribution to the common production process, in opposition to the individualistic and private attitudes characterising the contemporary neoliberal regime.

From our perspective, it is not possible to speak of *the commons* in theoretical terms only without referring, at the same time, to *commoning practices*. In other words, practices such as collective actions/relationships, de-commodified behaviour mechanisms, as well as experiments with solidarity carried out by inclusive communities give real meaning to the concept of *the commons*. These practices are able to raise people's awareness about direct democracy processes that are mobilised around a *common material or immaterial experience*, thus taking into consideration also the issue of an equal distribution of wealth produced by such collective activation.

This consideration brings us concretely towards the realisation of Commonfare, a new *welfare of the common* that is already produced and *supported* by these self-organised and self-regulated organisations where new social, economic and cultural subjectivation processes as well as new relations can arise.

This is a system of peculiar social relations (community-based, cooperative-based, trust-based) aimed at promoting the shared use of the resources available to a community that tries to create an autonomous mutual support process through which people and experiences mutually reinforce each

⁴ <https://commonfare.net/it/stories/mondeggi-nuovo-anno-stesso-copione>

⁵ <https://commonfare.net/it/stories/un-isola-verde-all-isola-la-storia-di-isola-pepe-verde-giardino-condiviso-a-milano>

⁶ They are, not by chance, the same areas we have highlighted in the description of welfare measures in the three pilot countries.

⁷ See D2.1, Overturing teh PIE Conditions: stories and experiences of Communities pag. 73.

other⁸. However, analysing these practices, we cannot hide the fact that the issue of *resource* and *time* scarcity recurs continuously. These two elements (time and income) need to be taken into account when suggesting the horizon of a new possible welfare system (*Commonfare*), which draws inspiration from the need to provide a *structured framework* for bottom-up practices and needs. Developing practices that break with traditional capitalistic logic can be difficult and time consuming. It might take time for the promoter of these practices to achieve their goals in terms of sustainability, for example their ability to distribute income. The fact that people need a job to earn some money influences and limits their choices and *desires*, thus affecting the sustainability of the good practices themselves. The desire to relate to others, which is crucial for the collective experiences we analysed in the project, seems often mortified. The *mortification of the desire* is part of a disturbing picture which includes the commercialisation of human feelings within the bio-economy⁹. On the one hand, we witness the decline of the traditional Fordist wage labour, and on the other hand, the process of creation of wealth (valorization) is more and more based on the appropriation of both natural scarce goods and human faculties (thought, language and body): social relationships and cooperation thus characterize the current mode of production – even though they do not include the totality of contemporary production dynamics.

While we witness the decline of the traditional Fordist wage labour, we enter in a situation in which it is not the worker who is exploited but the *person* as a whole, who is then urged to compete with others in a *race for survival*.¹⁰ Therefore, on the one hand, shortage of time and lack of income tend to reduce the desire for participation in collective projects, thus encouraging the creation of an *economic ego* that isolates herself, fears competition from the outside world, and prefers to pursue her own benefit, that is, to keep her own life going. On the other hand, the obligations associated with the possibility of receiving forms of income support in Europe might impede commitment to common projects, that is, the activation of civic society. Yet, many of the collective experiences observed during the project are at least partially capable of responding to personal needs and they have been undoubtedly addressing the issue how to satisfy them and the equally decisive one related to the concatenations and circuits that need to be implemented in order to solidify their existence/subsistence.

We, therefore, reckon that institutional actors should take into account the possibility of finding a possible answer to the difficulties caused by the social and economic crisis that Europe is facing in the forms of funding suggested in the *Commonfare* model, which is based on basic income¹¹ and the

8 Massimo De Angelis, *Omnia Sunt Communia. On The Commons and the Transformation to Postcapitalism*, The University City of Chicago Press Books, 2017; Silvia Federici, *Reincantare il mondo. Femminismo e politica dei commons*, Ombre Corte, Verona 2018.

9 Arlie Russell Hochschild, *The Managed Heart: Commercialization of Human Feeling*, University of California Press, Berkeley 1983

¹⁰ To better analyse this aspect, see P. Dardot, C. Laval, *The New Way of the World: On Neoliberal Society*, Verso, London, 2017

11 Philippe Van Parijs, Yannick Vanderborght, *Basic Income: A Radical Proposal for a Free Society and Sane Economy*, Harvard University, March 2017

recognition of an eco-system of tangible and intangible common goods. The notion of an *eco-system of services* represents an important attempt to move from a society centred on private capital, towards a *caring society*, meant as Maria Puig de la Bellacasa has reconceptualised it: *care* entails something that is inevitable, and yet changeable, variable and not influenced by essentialist or moral norms, and whose framework should be moved beyond the human and its temporality. So, it is above all necessary to “think with care”, a “difficult and not idyllic (not innocent)”¹² requisite of collective thinking in interdependent worlds. Care is, therefore, a force distributed across a multiplicity of agencies and materials in more than human worlds¹³.

Therefore it should be recommended that institutions should actively promote **the implementation of policies to finance these varied common goods (good practices) measuring the value of these initiatives outside a market logic**. Institutions often find themselves unable to allocate resources for social spending, however it has been already noted that “the evaluation of the production of the common good will turn basic income into an investment rather than a social expenditure. An investment in a different type of production: the production of public goods and services that belong to the community and cannot be privatised”¹⁴.

Obviously, it is necessary to pay attention to the risks of segmentation and *subsumption* that some new interpretations of a private-based welfare system can bring with them. It is, therefore, important to assess whether the appropriation of a common good takes place in a corporative way or if we are facing actual cooperative processes that are capable of fostering the development of a solidarity economy as well as other values that go beyond the single actor's profit.

Fig.04

12 Maria Puig de la Bellacasa, *Matters of Care. Speculative Ethics in More Than Human Worlds*, University of Minnesota Press, Minneapolis London 2017, pag. 19

13 Ivi, pag. 187

14 Susana Martin Belmonte “Risorse per il reddito di base” in Andrea Fumagalli, Gianni Giovannelli, Cristina Morini (edit by), *La rivolta della cooperazione. Sperimentazioni sociali e autonomia del possibile*, Mimesis, Milano 2018, Pag. 122

1.2. COMMONFARE AND SOCIAL INNOVATION

We can define Commonfare as a new idea of welfare where basic income is considered to be the pivot around which an *ecosystem of services* based on tangible and intangible common goods revolves. Commonfare takes into account the vital fabric of a society that is autonomously and *rhizomatically* striving to foster a collective understanding and management of *risk* in order to oppose the extremely emphasised trend towards the *individualisation of risk*. However, when thinking of the Welfare of the Common it is necessary to take into account the concept of *common* in the singular form¹⁵. The *common* is a set of language, communication, reproduction and relational practices, which are an integral part of human life and sociality. But if the common becomes the origin of the development of learning and networking processes, it bends to the capitalist needs of the productive structure. as the same Common.

The *common* is therefore becoming the basis for the accumulation of bio-cognitive capitalism and can take different forms depending on the modalities of accumulation, that is, whether they are based on the exploitation of the cognitive-formative faculties, or on relational-cooperative faculties. In a first approximation, we could name the former *cognitive common*, and the latter *re/productive common*. The common represents social cooperation, which is expressed in the *general intellect* and *social reproduction*. This difference needs to be clear, because the expropriation of the common goes beyond the dichotomy between private and public property, whose dialectic addresses the issue related to the management and use of privatised or state-owned *common goods*.¹⁶ In this dialectic between *common* (as input) and *common goods*, (as output) including for instance, knowledge new forms of contemporary welfare, arise and develop in the space between privatization and workfare..

The process of social innovation produced by the practices that the Commonfare-Pie News project has encountered and highlighted, places itself in this new social context. These new practices are able to widen the welfare provision in a context where public welfare is subject to continuous restrictions and to financialization processes.

With the spread of the neoliberal policies, Welfare institutions are increasingly becoming subject to “capitalistic processes”. More importantly, they are managed directly by the private market hierarchy. Keynesian public welfare is no longer sustainable on the basis of the constraints imposed on public budget, and is gradually replaced by forms of *Workfare*. The *Workfare* is not a universal system of social assistance (like the Keynesian one). It is a selective and a self-financed welfare system, as in most of today's European social security systems, which is functional for the process of privatisation of healthcare, education, and social security, and that is complementary to the so-called “subsidiarity

15 C. Vercellone made a point of the concept of the *common in the singular form* compared to that of common good (*or common in the plural form*). For a more detailed discussion, see Carlo Vercellone, Francesco Brancaccio, Alfonso Giuliani, Pierluigi Vattimo, *Il Comune come modo di produzione. Per una critica dell'economia politica dei beni comuni*, Ombre Corte, Verona, 2017, especially cap. 2.

16 A. Fumagalli, *Economia politica del comune*, DeriveApprodi, Roma, 2017

principle”, according to which the State can only intervene when the objectives set cannot be satisfactorily achieved by the private market. The Social innovation of the good practices, lies precisely in experimenting with new forms of welfare that go beyond the Fordist Welfare State and the increasingly privatised and financialised *Workfare*.

*The Manifesto for Commonfare*¹⁷ produced during the project, outlines three key features:

1. an unconditional basic income as a kind of monetary compensation (remuneration) of social productivity, which is not recognised yet;
2. free access to those common goods (both tangible and intangible) that allow individuals to self-determine themselves both in the material sphere (healthcare, housing, mobility) and in the subjective-relational sphere (education, culture, socialising) so as to allow the potential re-appropriation of their own *common*;
3. the availability of an alternative monetary circuit based on a digital currency (*commoncoin*) able to ensure both sustainability and economic autonomy of the welfare of the common and to define the tools for its funding.

Fig. 05

¹⁷ General Intellect Collective, *Commonfare or Welfare of the Commonwealth: towards a manifesto*, in I. Gloerich, G. Lovinck, P. De Vries (eds.), *MoneyLab Reader 2: Overcoming the Hype*, Institute of Net Cultures, Amsterdam, 2018; <http://pieproject.eu/2018/01/22/the-launch-of-the-manifesto-for-commonfare/>

1.3 PLATFORMS, COMMUNICATION, PARTICIPATION: CREATING LINKS

The good practices that joined the platform represent therefore a potential antidote to the welfare systems' subjection to a *new mode of production*, which is functional to capital accumulation. These practices are able to activate a complete cycle for supplying the social good they intend to offer (from production to distribution). To this end, it is necessary that these good practices are able to coordinate themselves in a positive synergy and complementarity. That is to say, they should be able to create positive externalities in the territories they work in, in order to achieve two fundamental goals. On the one hand, they should provide a cohesive welfare package that is fit for the needs and requirements (as well as desires) of the reference territory. On the other hand, they should promote a network of mutual aid among the same good practices in order to support their own sustainability and economic and political autonomy.

With reference to this practice and methodology of organisation, it is possible to speak of **social innovation**, regardless of the need met. It follows that a necessary (although not sufficient) condition is that the good practices work as a network. Contemporary technologies provide digital platforms capable of creating interconnections between individuals who have heterogeneous goals. In most cases, we see that these platforms belong to what has been defined platform capitalism¹⁸, that is, a new business model that is able to exploit the social nature of people and meet the demand for services. Platforms operating within the platform capitalism are key instruments in the process of accumulation of private profits and they ensure, above all, a high market capitalisation, whether they are a social network or a food delivery platform. They allow, at the same time, both extraction of the "value of networking"¹⁹ and organisation, work intermediation and life practices. If Facebook, to make an example, relies on free participation and passive consent of its users to collect large amounts of data to be used for profiling and advertising²⁰ and the management of human time, Deliveroo, or other similar platforms, profit from the introduction of rating systems. In the former case, we face a process of extraction of the value of networking, in the latter case modern and advanced labour exploitation processes are enacted.

In this context, the concept of platform turns out to be ambiguous and ambivalent. This ambiguity also affects those platforms that intend to develop sharing processes (*sharing economy*) based on a

18 N. Srnicek, N. *Platform Capitalism*; Polity Press: Cambridge, UK, 2018

19 A. Fumagalli, "Per una teoria del valore-rete: Big data e processi di sussunzione" in D. Gambetta (ed.), *Datacrazia. Società, Cultura e Conflitti al Tempo dei Big Data*; D Editore, Roma, Italy, 2018

20 AAVV, *Big Data, Webfare e reddito per tutti. Siamo in rete produciamo valore, vogliamo reddito*, BIN Italia, Roma Marzo 2019, (ISSN 2611-5190).

peer-to-peer logic²¹. Trebor Scholz coined the term “platform cooperativism” (*cooperative platform*)²² as an opposition to platform capitalism and on the assumption that “corporate *sharing economy* is increasingly present”²³ today. The concept of platform cooperativism has three parts: first, it is about cloning the technological heart of Uber, Task Rabbit, Airbnb, or UpWork. It embraces the technology but wants to put it to work with a different ownership model, adhering to democratic values, in order to crack the broken system of the sharing economy/on-demand economy that only benefits the few²⁴. It is in this sense that platform cooperativism is about structural changes, including a change of ownership. Secondly, platform cooperativism is about solidarity. Platforms can be owned and operated by inventive unions, cities and various forms of cooperatives, everything from multi-stakeholder and work-owned co-ops to producer-owned cooperatives, but it should be clear that it is about producing use value rather than exchange value. In other words, the platform should be non-profit and the user is, at the same time, co-owner and producer of contents. Thirdly, it is about achieving goals. Platform cooperativism is built on the reframing of concepts like **innovation** and **efficiency** with an eye on benefiting all, not just exploiting profits for the few. Platform capitalism is amazingly ineffective in taking care of people, while the main goal of platform cooperativism is the well-being of all participants.

It is within this framework that we asked ourselves some questions about the role played by a platform like Commonfare.net. This is a tool designed to connect existing welfare *good practices* in order to promote, through interaction and mutual knowledge, the creation of autonomous networks, including financial ones, that can facilitate sustainability. Thus, encouraging an alternative Welfare model, the welfare of the common (*Commonfare*). This is the challenge that the project addressed. **success underlies the sustainability of platform itself in the future.**

Is there a need/desire to communicate and put online what we already do? Would it possible to overcome the self-referential nature of individual experiences (while maintaining their own identity necessary for the action to take place and make sense in the context of reference) so that they join in a project of autonomy/sustainability (and safeguard) of the *common*? Do good practices risk, in some case, meeting only the demands made by minorities, that is, being too tied to specific needs of specific groups (migrants, artists, women, LGBTQ communities, young people, unemployed)? Is a communication tool outside the logic of ownership and profit which is necessary in order to strengthen the overall ability to “create critical mass” in the territories where good practices work? Is it necessary to regard a platform as a means of production to be liberated and self-managed according to the principle of solidarity, respect for privacy, creation of forms of mutualism and relations between people so that everyone can benefit from it?

21 M. Bauwens, *The political economy of peer production*. Ctheory, 2005. <http://www.ctheory.net/articles.aspx?id=499>

22 T. Scholz, *Platform Capitalism*, <http://www.rosalux-nyc.org/platform-cooperativism-2/>

23 Ibidem, p. 10.

24 AAVV, *Redditto garantito e innovazione tecnologica, tra algoritmi e robotica*, BIN Italia, Asterios, Trieste Italy, June 2017

The project brought to the foreground unique experiences in Italy, Croatia and the Netherlands that show how a positive answer to these questions is urgent. The hypothesis underlying this European project, namely the idea that civic society – even in very different cultural and political contexts – is able to highlight social self-organisation practices capable of prefiguring a new way of building “society” despite the imposition of austerity measures and policies aimed at dismantling the welfare state, is indeed confirmed by the existence of such collective experiences. Now, we would like to focus on the role the platform can play and its sustainability.

Fig.06

2. THE MEANING OF SUSTAINABILITY FOR THE COMMONFARE CONSORTIUM

The concept of sustainability should be oriented towards the harmonisation of the temporal dimensions of the past (i.e. learning from experience), as well as the present and the future. It is, therefore, about analysing how the benefits of an action can continue beyond the funding period. One of the key challenges for continuous sustainability is the ability to listen to demands and make new choices requiring commitment and responsibility. The risks of sustainability of a specific artefact (commonfare.net), as well as a collective proposal (Commonfare), require a transparent monitoring process as well as transparent paths adopted for change.

The consortium has produced a Mid Term Internal Report aiming to reflect on the initiatives carried out, the relations undertaken, the criticalities faced between month 10 and 21, in order to have a plan to re-orient actions towards commonfare.net sustainability.

The Mid Term Report has produced a template containing different fields that can be traced back to macro categories:

- ▶ Potential sustainability: financial/economic feasibility; ownership by target groups.
- ▶ Horizontal issues: this category includes also two aspects/questions associated with factors of sustainability (Is there a clear commitment and an adequate ownership by the project partners?).
- ▶ Cross-cutting issues: practical and strategic interests, governance.

In this section we will often recall statements included in the Mid-Term Report produced from the different partners (M24), as a key futures for the sustainability plan of commonfare.net. The partners' words build a common and collective novel and outline the profile of what will have to be kept

constantly in mind for the future.

Trust. *'The capacity of the consortium/platform to attract, first a sufficient number of end-users in order to demonstrate the potential of the platform [...] the capacity of the commonshare/reputation to support the creation of long term and stable trust relationships among participants within the platform'* (AU).

Participative governance. *'The capacity of commonfare.net and of (part of) the consortium to continue to be engaged with the management, design, and dissemination of commonfare.net and of commonfare as a concept[...] with a sense of ownership of commonfare.net by the commoners, exercised through participation in the governance of the platform and through growing solidarity with others'* (M-ITI).

Original and replicable. *'Substantial and original contribution with actionable knowledge on digital social innovation, and, second, developing and evaluating a methodology for large-scale co-design projects, a methodology that other can then replicate, adapt their specific needs and improve'*(UNITN).

Community. *'Commonfare.net is seen [...] useful to individuals and organizations [...] creating a sense of community, i.e. that individuals feel invested in the concept of Commonfare'* (CMS).

Benefits. *'[...] coming from the Commonfare [...] a clear identity, although a multiple one, that is able to attract people and experiences that use it in order to build real opportunities'* (BIN ITALIA).

Timeline. *'Platform that can run at cost with as less negative externalities as possible at least for the next 25 years'* (Dyne) and *'ensuring resources for the continuation/development of cf.net after the PIE News project'* (FBK).

Fig.07

2.1. ATTRACTIVENESS, CRITICALITIES AND IMPLEMENTATION OF COMMONFARE SUSTAINABILITY

2.2.1 ATTRACTIVENESS: A CONCEPT, A SPACE, A POSSIBILITY.

The **concept** of Commonfare creates innovation as it *'is an innovative platform in many ways; an intersection of technology and society experiment [...] to conduct action-research'* (AU), that starting from *socio-technical solution* reconnects social theory, and intervention in the field *'to critical thinking and political activism, and combines social sciences, technology design, and activism'* (M-ITI) *'as a ground for political experimentation and experimenting in real life'* (UNITN) able to foster the *'involvement of people on common needs, for changing perspective'* (FBK).

A **space** specifically designed to foster the production of the Common *'designed to foster the production of the Common, condition of possibility and result of biopolitical production'* (Dyne). A space for reflection, recognition and exchange *'Time for reflection, space dedicated to the emergence and recognition of non-commodified goods and a place able to both give visibility to their projects and create synergy with others'* (BIN Italia), where to experiment with Commonshare *'to experiment with novel ideas, i.e. commonshare'* (AU) and share information *'sharing information [...] to connect with those with similar interests or else similar problems, and being able to view best practices and news stories'* (CMS).

A **possibility** to enhance a common doing, the ability to envision an alternative welfare model *'to show the potential of alternative solidarity-based networks. The attractiveness of Commonfare comes from the fact that it rouses the imagination, for it evokes innovative social, economic and relational models'* (BIN ITALIA). A possibility to connect people and Good Practices overcoming distances and logistical difficulties through an attractive platform, offering *'practices and news stories from outside Croatia, and around Europe, can empower individuals in Croatia to do the same, and reproduce best practices and information sharing across borders is also seen as a very attractive element of our platform'* (CMS), to provide and receive support beyond institutional welfare measures and experiment alternative models through Commoncoin (All partners).

2.2.2 CRITICALITIES: INVOLVEMENT, RESOURCES, DISTRUST

It is necessary to **involve** a large number of Commoners *'growing the user base will be a main challenge and perhaps the most critical point for achieving success. That of growing the user-base is something that the consortium will need to achieve in a relatively short time'* (AU) as well as institutional actors, such as influencers and the press who can increase both the visibility and the user-base: *'it is important to reach out to the engaged press (blogs and digital venues more in general mainly) in order to make the project visible as much as possible; at the same time, it is important to foster collaboration between media and cultural researchers and media practitioners'* (M-ITI).

Secondly, it must be considered that Commonfare is a new concept, which still needs to be analysed in depth from a theoretical point of view in order to make it easier to understand (M-ITI, AU). If the number of users is not sufficient and the exchanges among people are inadequate, the results in terms of effectiveness will be irrelevant *'the risk of a lack of reciprocity in exchanges'* (Dyne).

Time is a **resource** that has not always been possible to manage in an optimal way to maintain a high level of people's involvement *'people entering and exiting the precarious labour market with a certain "dynamism" who are not always "available" in terms of time to "follow" a process of active engagement in the project'* (BIN ITALIA). Underestimating the time necessary for the platform back-end (FBK) and finding sufficient **financial resources** to keep the method intact: *'gaining more funding to conduct further research [...] this requires the mixing of well-organized and structured project design, able to accommodate for contingencies and novel results and events while keeping some integrity on the methodological point of view'* (M-ITI) without giving in to commercial developments has certainly been a criticality *'people in contemporary Western society are increasingly addressed by commercial and other entities (e.g. marketing, surveys) makes it difficult to engage people, especially when scepticism is in place'* (UNITN).

Also, the political connotation of the Commonfare term/concept brings with it a potential for **distrust** when one interacts with people who do not come from the same background: *'the term Commonfare seems to have a political and cultural connotation, and therefore it might not have a great appeal in contexts and among people who do not already have a certain wealth of knowledge'* (BIN ITALIA); beside, **people distrust the platform as a tool**, for they are not used to using it on a daily basis *'significantly less interest in providing information for others to the platform and much less keen to write their stories and share them on the platform (because of embarrassment, feeling unfamiliar or uncomfortable sharing personal stories on the internet, and scepticism about privacy online)[...]Uncertainty/ insecurity over the use of digital currencies [...]The use of collaborative economy websites, sharing economy websites, and digital currencies/crypto currencies is quite low in Croatia [...] so there is a general apprehension amongst the public to use such tools'* (CMS).

2.2.3 IMPLEMENTATION: RECOGNISING INTERDEPENDENCE

Because of its complex nature, the Consortium considered some key elements for commonfare.net sustainability.

Trust. The capacity of the consortium/platform to attract, first a sufficient number of end-users in order to demonstrate the potential of the platform [...] (AU).

Participative Governance. The capacity of commonfare.net and of (part of) the consortium to continue to be engaged with the management, design, and dissemination of commonfare.net and of commonfare as a concept[...] with a sense of ownership of commonfare.net by the commoners, exercised through participation in the governance of the platform and through growing solidarity with others (M-ITI).

Original and replicable. Substantial and original contribution with actionable knowledge on digital social innovation, and, second, developing and evaluating a methodology for large-scale co-design projects, a methodology that other can then replicate, adapt their specific needs and improve (UNITN).

Community. Commonfare.net is seen [...] useful to individuals and organizations [...] creating a sense of community, i.e. that individuals feel invested in the concept of Commonfare (CMS).

The interdependence between the concept of *Commonfare*, the *commonfare.net* platform and the *commoners* social and economic conditions represent a crucial point to be analysed with regard to sustainability: enhancing non-commodified forms of cooperation, by reversing the models of contemporary society based on individualism, and the visibility of concrete proposals mutually fuel their possibilities, attractiveness, impact and transformation.

Therefore, sustainability is about dissemination of real or potential outcomes of its contents, either directly, by imitation, or indirect stimulus. The commonfare.net promotion activity was geared towards the development of a *learning community* where cooperative tendency and collaborative approach were a key factor to increase the attractiveness of Commonfare.net and its own strengths. The platform has actually aimed to the emergence of a common doing that can turn into collective activism through a process envisaging the progressive involvement of small groups and community-based organisations. However, this process cannot be confined to the specific project timing. Relations, experiences, social connections, as well as human capital that daily regenerates spaces, ideas, time and proposals imply a life and a time of its own.

Therefore, the concept of sustainability – both in terms of financial feasibility and ownership by commoners - entails the need to accept the fact that there are “different” times and forms. The immediacy of the proposal has produced activities and actions in some cases; in others, the social and

economic complexity caused people and collective experiences to face longer elaboration times to build paths. This project, as well as the Commonfare proposal, therefore deeply identifies with the contradictions of this era, for it is about the living bodies, the lives that experience these contradictions in everyday life. Fragmentation, atomization, precarisation of life, economic difficulties, and broken life times are not generic terms. They are material conditions that the Commonfare Pie-News project has faced while embedding into the flesh of the social body of reference. Thus, identifying flexible spaces and proposals has become necessary to find “a common time” for planning. Sustainability, whatever declination one may assume, cannot help but keep in mind this condition, which however does not define a starting point but a condition that is continually reproduced.

Fig.08

2.2.4. IMPLEMENTATION: TURNING CRITICALITIES INTO RESOURCES

Future sustainability, economic-financial feasibility, involvement of other actors (bottom-up good practices or other stakeholders) were some of the elements investigated during this process that led to many concrete actions aimed precisely at understanding possible solutions in defining and ensuring sustainability.

The Consortium has continually faced two challenges the dynamics that hinder an ongoing *commoners'* involvement, and the distrust towards digital platform and the issue of data protection.

When change is a dimension that looms over and interrupts stories (employment precariousness

brings along this element²⁵), the space for redesign takes on a disruptive urgency and even the relations that have started are suspended, put on hold: the *engagement* and promotion activities of commonfare.net had to deal with this dynamic, as well as with the vulnerability of mechanisms within groups or good practices subjected to a continuous pressure, for instance, on the issue of the eviction of the spaces they self-manage.

During the co-design and dissemination activities we often faced a clear distrust towards digital platforms and the *platform economy*. Due to different territorial, economic and digital culture contexts, this distrust oriented itself towards different aspects. For example in the Netherlands, where reflection and awareness on data control is widespread, the distrust was related to the ownership of information. On the contrary, in Croatia, where the use of collaborative economy websites and sharing economy websites is quite low, 'there is a general apprehension amongst the public to use such tools' (CSM). This distrust has led the consortium to develop a communication tool that is capable to convey the ethical dimension, which also affects the financial sustainability, for gaining more funding to conduct further research [...] requires some integrity on the methodological point of view' (M-ITI) without giving in to commercial developments precisely because 'people in contemporary Western society are increasingly addressed by commercial and other entities (e.g. marketing, surveys), [which] makes it difficult to engage people, especially when scepticism is in place' (UNITN).

Therefore, much attention has been paid to privacy protection in order to '*foster trust, to allow for autonomy and self-determination at all levels, and to allow commoners to feel protected, thereby setting the stage for them to act*' (UNITN) and legal protection in relation to the use of the Commoncoin have been ensured via '*research and analysis around legal and incorporation frameworks [...] crucial to be arranged in order to give more possibilities for long-term sustainability of platform*' (Dyne).

The ability of the Consortium to create effective communication on these points, to manage relationships in a flexible way, by accompanying them in a more extended time and modulating the proposals for participation and engagement in the different possible elements of meaning for each experience, has led to important outcomes.

During the meetings between the partners of the Consortium, between pilot countries and stakeholders, or with the collective experiences encountered in the field, different proposals emerged (see Figure 13,14,15). All of them were collected so as to provide a range of options, reflections, and formulas for sustainability. For instance, '*Developing a local network including some good practices possibly supported by a local institution (either a local administration or an academic body) that can share resources (either human or economic resources) could represent another step to participate for the sustainability*' (BIN Italia). As well as "*building a pilot in Trento by developing territorial marketing (FBK)*", or keep "*organising Networking Events, training activities with the good practices*" (CMS).

²⁵ AAVV BIN Italia, *Generazioni Precarie. Una conricerca tra percezione del rischio, bisogni emergenti, welfare dal basso*, Common Book Series N°1, Università di Trento, Feb 2019

Moreover, also providing continuity in terms of *'Involving students and engaging them in social innovation projects linked to Commonfare by increasing local visibility that would allow us for fostering a local network of stakeholders'* (UNITN). In the same way, the involvement of institutions, political decision-makers, academies, and universities should continue *'to involve them and foster their collaboration with commoners and "good practices"'* (UNITN).

Sustainability is *'subordinated to the needs of the pilot partners in engaging with the local contexts'* (M-ITI), but also to the innovation of the technological tool *'demonstrating the replicability of the 'reputation' approach used by Commonfare.net and support the work for the dashboard in relation to the network dynamics [...] will be a fundamental milestone for the long term success of commonfare.net as a CAPS platform and a demonstration that our approach to "reputation" may work for other platforms'* (AU).

- ▶ Developing and creating theoretical, methodological and technological tools has meant meeting the needs that came from the field research without renouncing to the academic rigour that research requires: *'Overall, the project has produced interesting research results and thus the engagement with the scientific community is very positive'* (AU); *"The Community Informatics Research Network is in general enthusiastic [...] and very interested in following its results; Associations are open to find a role of synergy [...]"* (FBK); *"while the academic and project proposals colleagues have always shown enthusiasm'* (M-ITI); *"Academic and scientific community and other EU projects expressed high interest in terms of fieldwork activities, user engagement and ethics.'*(UNITN).

Having interacted with precarious workers has therefore meant "keeping up with the times" of people involved, rather than just "keeping the project on schedule".

- ▶ Commoners very much appreciated the proposal as a whole and eagerly took part in the project: *"Grass-roots organisations, associations and local communities. All of them were highly interested in the project [...] to the point that at times they pushed for the organisation of meetings and public initiatives"* (BIN Italia).

The graph below which reports on the platform user registrations shows a constant increase in participation but also tries to display the participation trends in line with the considerations on the nature of time and investment that Commoners have transferred on the platform, too.

Fig. 09 Dynamics of commonfare.net registered users

The Commonfare.net platform gathered a process of collective storytelling, and collected more than 300 stories which has been read by several thousands of people. This aspect was clear since the beginning (also in relation to the communication activity carried out through social media), and it becomes even more evident as the platform consolidation process goes along. Yet again, the comparison with the pervasive use of global social media (above all, Facebook) calls for reflections on how Commonfare.net managed to do an important job and on the time required for its consolidation: by activating the strength of cooperation it has been possible to build a space where stories were about a 'common doing' that already exists and wants to find visibility, support and new connections. A 'common doing' that wants to find a space for promoting and networking that is more appropriate for its own value dimension, out of the predatory logic of global platforms.

Together, that is, within common experience, this awareness strengthens itself and commonfare.net has been seen as an opportunity. On the contrary, this awareness loses its strength in the private action of everyday life, and the massive use of Facebook or Instagram makes the emergence of a different need more complicated. This reflection inevitably entails that participation is the main resource ensuring sustainability.

Therefore, we will not refer to the mere economic aspect of sustainability, that is, finding resources,

for even if it was easy to find them, the lack of *Commoners'* participation would make it useless. The capital itself of the Commonfare platform depends on participation, the role it plays, how social use gives recognition to this platform. This is the real resource, which justifies the need for a financial dimension, and gives meaning to sustainability over time.

These considerations may help envisage the path commonfare.net should take for its sustainability. The effort that should be made (both in terms of activation and design) is to enhance that human capital, those community-based organisations, those stories of the common, those social experiences we have encountered that are the actual wealth for commonfare.net.

The point of departure and arrival are, in this sense, alike. Ensuring this gaze, the connection between the “stories of the possible”, networking and exchange – also through the use of commoncoins – is the main focus.

By transposing, the possible equation is CMC^2 (Commoners – Money – Commoners²) rather than MCM^2 (Money – Commoners – Money²).

Fig. 10 Commoners social value participation

The meaning of this representation is that experience and participation of people and communities that create and use money (whether real or virtual) to increase participation and exchange of relations, as well as a common doing, should be put at the core of the production of social value. Therefore, two main categories should be taken into account in terms of sustainability: people and resources, as well as the interaction between them (people/people, people/resources, people as resources, people/time/money). These ingredients are essential for a project that aims to encourage relationships in order to experiment with different and effective social cooperation in order to develop alternative economic systems.

Fig. 11 Overview of the Commonfare platform

In order to make the ownership from the *commoners* one of the main strengths of sustainability, it is necessary a long term planning including not only economic support but also a continuous involvement of commoners.

3. SUSTAINABILITY AS A WAY

Fig 12

It is worth emphasising that all the hypotheses elaborated pivot on the principle of ensuring accessibility and ownership by the *commoners*, the maximum satisfaction of their needs, the protection of the basic principles and values, continuity of the platform and, thus, the inception of trust-based relationships between all those involved. These elements can be therefore considered the infrastructure of all reflections, as well as the pivot around which the definition of sustainability scenarios and hypotheses revolves. The consortium partners are deeply aware that the different scenarios can be implemented gradually and that, consequently, it is necessary to ensure intermediate scenarios. As a result, various transition hypotheses emerge in order to ensure platform consolidation and complete *ownership* by those who already use the platform, and those who will join it in the future so as to achieve financial sustainability.

In this perspective of circular economy, “*biological nutrients*” (people, stories, cooperation and connection among them, exchange of skills and re-use of what is outside the mainstream circuits of production) and the *technological ones*, which are designed to be used rather than consumed through a *functional service* mode, interact so that those who produce and those who use them always keep ownership, responsibility and control.

On this basis, various options involving all project partners have been gradually developed. Thus, the solution that took place entails the establishment of a new legal entity (see section 3.1) in order to ensure continuity, participation and visibility at the same time.

Simultaneously, in order to ensure the continuity of the constituent values it is also necessary to deal with the identification of diversified forms of funding at the local, national and international levels. However, the primary idea is that it is necessary to identify an *open source* sustainability that makes the wealth of human capital, either inside or outside the current project consortium, the key ensuring open and democratic *governance*, participation, empowerment, enhancement of human capital, forms of collaborative economy. In short, making ‘common doing’ feasible and replicable.

Among the various proposals collected and discussed, we show below the three macro options emerged in the Mid Term Report, which tended to highlight some common needs that have then inspired further actions.

Fig. 13 Sustainability scenario n. 1

Fig.14 Sustainability scenario n. 2

Fig. 15 Sustainability scenario n. 3

The three options has contributed to the definition of a concrete and shared hypothesis about sustainability. *'The platform concepts and technology could be pitched to new entities, such as Foundations and other non-profit organisations (beyond the EU commission funding).'* (AU); *'Core services should be managed by an independent board, additional could be managed leveraging on external institutions, through a specific legal agreement.'* (FBK); *'Commonfare to become a foundation, an association, or another kind of legal entity.'* (UNITN); *'At least one organization, member of the consortium, or a best practice taking over responsibility for the governance of the platform.'* (CMS). *'Through a specific legal agreement that defines values, objectives, rules and responsibility, governance can be ensured:*

- ▶ *by a body/institution able to ensure a new flow of funds both in terms of cash and human resources through identifying further research elements (that the consortium will be promoting);*
- ▶ *by the fact that a community takes up the management of Commonfare as a tool to make its community broader;*
- ▶ *by a subsidiarity-based management, which can be done through a 'non-definitive' formula such as the launch of a test period (including, for instance, research activities carried out by an academic body or a specific local institution, the introduction of such a tool in a given city, neighbourhood or region) useful to strengthen the platform.'* (BIN ITALIA).

On the basis of the reflections and suggestions collected from project partners, the issue of sustainability can be divided into two main topics:

- ▶ The first has to do with the practical and financial sustainability of the project;
- ▶ The second has to do with the promotion and dissemination of the most innovative elements of the project, starting from both the proposal of Commonfare and the implementation of technical support (platform). The two aspects are interdependent and mutually nourish each other, therefore they must be dealt with jointly.

Enhancing the role cooperation plays between different actors in an open and collective process is the key strength for a solid sustainability plan entailing the idea of a “new social project” that no longer takes account of roles but rather identifies the common reasons why these actors walk together. As if, once the project is completed, a new life takes shape, an autonomous one.

For this reason, the starting point, namely ensuring continuity of the platform, promoting Commonfare, the vitality of relationships and the development of new ones, is very important.

Fig. 16

3.1 NEW LEGAL ENTITY PARTICIPATORY GOVERNANCE. THE SETTING UP OF COMMONFARE ASSOCIATION

Being aware, on the one hand, that the outcomes achieved at the end of the third year do not fully express the potential of Commonfare.net, and on the other hand, that the values, objectives and solutions identified represent a heritage to be carefully supported, the consortium is aimed to identify a homogeneous vision that, as mentioned before, can act as multiplier. The option identified is the creation of a new legal entity that:

- ▶ Ensures compliance with Commonfare values by acting as promoter of the proposal;
- ▶ Acts as a guarantor for the continuity of the commonfare.net platform;
- ▶ Maintains a high level of attention on the different research and experimentation plans;
- ▶ Ensures the continuity of the already established relationships and creates new ones;
- ▶ Identifies various forms of financial support and funding;
- ▶ Ensures that the platform works and takes full responsibility for it;
- ▶ Promotes participation in the Commonfare Association.

The choice made is to promote the creation of an Association whose Statute is consistent with the following strategic dimensions:

Social sustainability. By facilitating participation in forms of exchange and enhancement, Commonfare.net plays an active role in enabling social cohesion, and thus, the formation of long-term sustainable social relations. Thanks to its features, it provides people with an opportunity to know experiences of cooperation and exchange where everyone has the same opportunities, thus reducing social inequalities and rather highlighting the strength of cooperation. The choice made to take this path ensures, therefore, that the existing relationships keep going on in compliance with the ethical values that inspired it.

Financial sustainability. Commonfare.net has been able to find a balance between human and financial resources also during the planning and design phase. In this sense, the Association endorses the capital of relations and skills of all founders and commoners.

On the financial front, Fondazione Bruno Kessler, Trento, Italy, has accepted to host the platform on its servers for around one year, final bureaucratic needs are being addressed, at the time of writing. A formal agreement between FBK and the Association will be formalized soon.

Temporal sustainability. The Association places itself in a medium-term dimension, being aware that the platform will have to change itself in order to reduce the risk of obsolescence, and then move to a completely self-managed and self-powered management by the commoners themselves.

3.2 COMMONFARE SUSTAINABILITY MODEL

Since Month 22, the Consortium has regularly reflected about the implementation of a sustainability model that could take into account the actual resources, the organisational and financial elements, the promotional capability, the skills, and the main stakeholders.

Key Partner

The founding members of the Commonfare Association can rely on professionalism and expertise in the following strategic areas: management, research, design and planning, social media communication, fund raising.

Key activities

For the first year, the main activities identified are:

- ▶ Management, monitoring and evaluation activities that allow for greater implementation of features also in relation to new needs that could arise from relating to other social and scientific communities;
- ▶ Actions supporting the technological infrastructure; continuous management and activation of contents both on the platform and through its social channels;
- ▶ Searching for new sources of funding and promoting fund raising campaigns.

Value proposition

The consolidation of the platform and the value generated in it (in social, relational, cooperation and opportunity terms) is the main goal of the Association. For this reason, the following principles are identified:

- ▶ The concept of Commonfare;
- ▶ Refuse commercialisation;
- ▶ Ensure and protect privacy and accessibility;
- ▶ Open and collaborative technologies;
- ▶ Safe and trust community.

Relationship and participation

For the short term, maximum attention will be given to the consolidation, construction and activation of networks with other social and scientific communities, and other transnational partnerships in which some founders are involved, and to the production of materials and promotional initiatives. The aim is to attract new *commoners* and possible institutional and social actors, such as unions and workers networks throughout Europe.

In particular, some guidelines are identified:

- ▶ Ground participation on local communities (more than national pilots) leveraging on a local leader;
- ▶ Maintain connections with social movements;
- ▶ Maintain a lively social media presence;
- ▶ Build and maintain connection with engaged press and “influencers”;
- ▶ Effective incentive mechanisms and useful tools;
- ▶ Effective trust building mechanism;
- ▶ Reaching people at the cross-national level, translation in other languages.

The figure below summarises the functions/professional skills that form the basis of the available material and immaterial resources.

Fig. 17 New legal entity resources and output

Costs

For the first year (12 months), the founding members have created a pre-feasibility financial plan:

Tab. 1

No. resources	Function/Role	Days/month	Cost	Tot
3	Content developer	2	100	600
1	Tech developer	1	300	300
2	Social media man.	2	200	400
1	Foundraser	1	100	100
Tot month				1200
Tot 12 months				14400

Tab. 2

Cost Item	Cost 1st year
Server	200
Expenses for setting up the association	270
Expenses for public initiatives	1000
Printing	200
Total	1670

3.3 RESPONSIBILITY AND ACTION TAKEN

The choice to create a new legal entity that takes responsibility for carrying the Commonfare project forward is a sign of how people involved in this experience have not only built solid bonds but also acquired new and stimulating competences. The founding members of the Commonfare Association have developed concrete actions and involved their own networks in order to achieve maximum impact. Both Santarcangelo Festival in Santarcangelo di Romagna and OltrEconomia Festival in Trento (see Deliverable 5.3), where the Commonfare Association was formally established and launched, can serve as an example of this commitment.

The choice to set up the Association in conjunction with the closing event of the financed project demonstrated that what was possible to create thanks to the funding of the H2020 program has now an independent life.

Another element that draws attention to the actions already carried out to ensure financial sustainability and continuity of research and implementation is the participation (of different partners and many members) in the call for *Collaborative Approaches to cultural heritage for Social cohesion – dt-transformations-11-2019* whose design 13 partners from 8 European countries took part in. This project submission is based on some of the main acquisitions emerged from the Commonfare/Pie News experience as well as on the use of the commonfare.net platform as an intersection of design and research activities among social actors and cultural heritage professionals. On this occasion, a new synergy with different sectors and countries has been created, thus developing relationships that are part of the relational assets of the Commonfare Association, regardless of the outcome of the proposal submitted.

The expansion of Commonfare is just at the beginning. There are still many opportunities that can be opened and links that can be created. Researchers have turned into members, united by a bond including both scientific and social research (many other studies on participatory design, network dynamics, etc., can be carried out).

The achievable goal of building a European, large, plural, interdisciplinary, multidimensional, co-operating and alternative community that sees social cohesion as something concrete and accessible is what Commonfare-to-be consciously and responsibly represents.